

Education Practicum for Early Childhood Learning

By Edwin Amuga

Practicum A

Developmental Stage Review

The developmental stage is critical-literacy based along with the increase in language and literacy standards and testing when during early childhood education. Critical literacy is a crucial tool in teaching as a way of matching teaching, teaching materials and processes with the talents and needs of children. The stage requires the consideration and factoring in children's points of view in early childhood literacy teaching through creation of literacy teaching that responds and empowers to children's identities as a crucial way of understanding children and their learning needs as well as gaining insights and a way of learning for teachers.

As a way of cultivating critical literacy is children's early education, one of the most viable strategies used is factoring discourse in teaching. Through this, the lived experiences of children and home discourses are included in the learning process in terms of the way the society around them things, does things, feels and acts about a range of issues and what it values.

Another strategy is taking a critical perspective during teaching in which the read materials are assessed in the ways they look at issues and how they affect the lives, thoughts, and actions of children in their early education. Another strategy is a generative curriculum that looks into the needs in the communities and provides an outlet, a source of action or social justice.

Discourse and critical perspective in teaching can be implemented by not only teaching students how to read but also how the read materials positions in their lives, how the reading affects their lives, thinking and actions in relation to peers and the world as a whole. The generative curriculum is implemented by involving students in developing curriculum factoring in their lived experiences. Critical literacy is included in the curriculum development to positively impact on the teacher's thinking and beliefs in teaching early childhood education.

Developmentally Appropriate Environment

In the face of the ever-changing and competitive educational environments worldwide, teaching must be focused on ensuring quality education. Quality education has received a lot of attention around the world driving teachers into on-the-job training programs meant to enhance their professional development. Since education can be studied in a range of contexts including social, political, pedagogical, philosophical and psychological, Online teaching must, therefore, apply pedagogy. The multiple choice questions are designed to expose student weaknesses and the correct answers jumbled up to make it hard for students to mistakenly arrive at them. The data acquired from the students' performance in the examination will expose areas most students do not understand and education material and practice adjustment will be based on them.

There are noticeable ongoing developments and successes in the educational technology field that are affecting a gamut of changes to the traditional teaching methods that encourage same sustained or improved development in the teaching that teachers are willing and eager to involve themselves in. one of the major barriers to integration of technologies in training in many institutions around the world is the reluctance to implement change attributable to technology-

enhanced learning skill deficiencies and inexperience in applying them. Teachers that are not technologically savvy are not likely to take part in technologically enhanced learning programs and activities as they are disinclined and have preconceived views on the technologically enhanced tools, teaching, and learning.

Practicum B

A range of theories were incorporated in the early childhood education to produce the best results for proper assessment and learning practice and material improvement. The Knowles Andragogy adult learning theory is applicable as it focuses on the learning process including physical comfort, mutual trust and respect building, openness and acceptance rather than the learning content. After establishing that the students are motivated to learn, it calls for the adoption of the cognitive field theory since learning and behavior would be related to perception and experience. There was also reference to the cognitive development interaction theory since the students would base their learning on experience. The social cognitive theory by Albert Bandura was also factored in. It posits that learning and knowledge acquisition process is related to social interactions, experiences and media contexts. A student observes a model performing a behavior and its consequences together with a series of events and uses them to guide their own behaviors. Learning a behavior is, therefore, based on the punishments, rewards and outcomes and not through trails, failures and successes (Buschman, 2015). Learning also occurs with the close identification of the observer and the model and self-efficacy.

In the past, teachers used to teach students how to solve problems using a computation algorithm or traditional problem-solving strategies such as guess and check, working backward, pattern-looking and many other ways, but these are changing to solving problems first through

acquisition of habits, behaviors, and dispositions such as patience, positive attitude and perseverance in the students own abilities and trusting in themselves and developing self-confidence in inventing and developing their own problem-solving strategies. Students are also taught to learn from their mistakes and enjoy problem-solving which also, in turn, increases their chances of recognizing mistakes and correct errors in their logic and refine their understanding. Teachers use these mistakes to gain teaching insights. And not give answers but guide students to arrive at correct answers themselves.

Student-centered learning increases the chances of children enjoying learning which also increases when they experience the satisfaction of overcoming problem-solving challenges. This they achieve by employing patience and perseverance when solving problems. Teaching students how to arrive at answers themselves and allowing them to fully explore, discuss and compare problems with other problems helps increase their chances of improving problem-solving skills regardless of how long it takes them to arrive at the correct answers. Children should be accorded plenty of time to go about their thinking and problem-solving activities.

Young children should be allowed to communicate their solutions to problems with other children as this helps increase their enjoyment of the process as well as helps them reduce mistakes as they share and discuss the solutions with their peers. This is achieved through discourse in problem-solving as some children better understand problem-solving when peers teach more than when teachers do it. The use of discourse and solution sharing also helps some students enhance their language skills in mathematics.

Students should be allowed to become problem-solvers as their enjoyment of solving problems is increased when adults acknowledge their irregularities in their development. It is

imperative to accept the irregular nature of the development in solving problems which is a steady and continuous unique process that requires patience.

Intervention strategies

The recommendation is to focus reading with demonstrations and puzzles to help build background knowledge. Based on student interest in movement and jumping, learning strategies for students at this stage have to be customized in the form of games and combined with lessons. Other learning sessions involve using magnetic puzzles and letters to introduce and build learning. Through the above strategies, students are expected to remain responsive to learning and lessons and will show commitment to information and development in gaining knowledge.

Practicum C

Assessment Development

At the early stage of learning and development, one of the most suitable tools for collection of data and assessment of learning is the Mesmer First words Beyond First words assessment and recording on the record running sheet since students still learning. The first words test is aimed at assessing the comprehension and use of age-appropriate practical English. The test aimed to determine if the student can recognize simple words and phrases in both spoken and written familiar, day to day English. The Mesmer First words test is based on the ability to identify letters and sound them.

Social Development Mini-lesson

Four-year-old preschool students should be taken through a tutoring session and a phonics tile test. She will be asked to point out letters read to her out of the letter tiles laid out.

The reading session progressed into word tiles due to this lack of knowledge, as it was pointless to continue with the next two sections on reading.

The Yopp-singer test was aimed at testing the phonemic awareness. Phonemic awareness is the awareness that speech is made up of a series of sounds. Phonemically aware students are able to break words into constituent parts by removing sounds from words and isolating the beginning, the middle and the end sounds of a word. Children with lack of phonemic awareness are not able to benefit from exposure to print or phonics instruction. The Yopp-singer test was initially used as a screening tool to determine students with low phonemic awareness levels. The assessment is apt for the kindergarten student with an aim of continuing the test throughout the year for systematic instruction to be undertaken in small groups in accordance with the needs of the student. The student was subjected to 5 to 10 minutes administration of the Yopp-singer test aimed at measuring their ability to separate words into their constituent sounds. The words selected for the test were based on familiarity of words and analysis of features. To generate the interest of the student, the assessment was introduced as a game of words where an appropriate feedback is expected. The student was asked to separate the word item. For the answer to be marked as correct, all phonemes must be separated. Digraphs such as 'sh' and 'th' were counted as one phoneme.

The student was asked to segment a collection of 22 words and successfully segmented 17 words, namely, dog, keep, no, she, that, red, me, sat, lay, zoo, job, in, at, top, by and do. The student incorrectly segmented five words namely fine, wave, grew, race, three and ice. From the results of the test, the student can be considered to be having a very good phonemic awareness. To improve on phonemic awareness, the student was scheduled for such activities as reading aloud, singing word-game based songs, and playing word games. Research shows that Yopp-

singer test is reliable and related with other phonemic awareness measures and future levels of reading.

Works Cited

Buschman. Children who enjoy problem solving. *Teaching Children Mathematics*, 9(9), 539
(2015)..